

CEDA

Mission: “curation and facilitation”

“Managing complex datasets and accompanying information for reuse and repurpose”

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Slides stolen from Bryan N. Lawrence
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Context:

- What is CEDA? (1)
- Why is CEDA? (2)
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What is CEDA?

www.ceda.ac.uk

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

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Data Centres

The Centre for Environmental Data Archival is responsible for the running of the following data centres:

British Atmospheric Data Centre
NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

The British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC), NERC's designated data centre for the UK atmospheric science community, covering climate, composition, observations and NWP data.

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

The NEODC is NERC's designated data centre for Earth Observation data and is part of NERC's National Centre for Earth Observation.

IPCC Data Distribution Centre

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) DDC provides climate, socio-economic and environmental data, both from the past and also in scenarios projected into the future. Technical guidelines on the selection and use of different types of data and scenarios in research and assessment are also provided. UK Climate Projections.

The UK Solar System Data Centre

The UK Solar System Data Centre, co-funded by STFC and NERC, curates and provides access to archives of data from the upper atmosphere, ionosphere and Earth's solar environment.

- ➔ 582 logical filesets
- ➔ 953 TB primary data, 1.3 PB primary storage, 2.2 PB total disk.
- ➔ 93 servers, 30 hypervisors, 265 distinct computer systems (inc. VMs)
- ➔ 140 distinct disk partitions
- ➔ 89 million primary files

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Projects

CEDA aims to carry out projects that develop and enhance data and information services. This allows us to actively participate in emerging digital curation and informatics fields, and ultimately provide a better service for environmental science.

CEDA is presently involved in the following projects. For further information please select the title to go to the relevant website or contact CEDA for more information.

IS-ENES
Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling (IS-ENES) is an FP7 project, funded by the European Commission under the Capacities Programme, Integrating Activities. IS-ENES has started on March 2009 and will finish on February 2013.

ISIC
CESM - facility for Climate and Environmental Monitoring from Space
CEDA is one of four core partners in CESM, based in the International Space Innovation Centre (ISIC) at Hatfield, will be a national centre for space-based Climate Change and Earth observation data and services.

JASMIN "super-data-cluster"
The JASMIN "super-data-cluster" is being deployed to support the data analysis requirements of the UK and European climate and earth system modelling community. It consists of multi-Petabyte fast storage co-located with data analysis computing facilities, with satellite installations at Reading, Leeds and Bristol Universities.

LTDP
ESA Long-Term Data Preservation (LTDP)
CEDA is supporting the European Space Agency (ESA) in its programme for Long-Term Data Preservation (LTDP), providing management support and technical expertise to activities associated with European LTDP implementation and framework coordination.

NERC Data Discovery Service
CEDA is responsible for the web-service behind NERC's Data Discovery Service (DDS), harvesting metadata catalogues from NERC's designated data centres and collating them into one data discovery service.

ESPAS
ESPAS - Near-Earth Space Data Infrastructure for e-Science

Lots more

Approximate sizes (FTE): BADC, 8; NEODC, 3.5; SSDC, (0.75+0.75); DDC, 1.5; Projects, 8.5; Other, 1
Total (2012/13): 24

Why is CEDA?

NERC Data Policy

- Ensure the **continuing availability** of environmental data of long-term value for **research, teaching, and for wider exploitation** for the public good, by individuals, government, business and other organisations.
- Support the **integrity, transparency and openness** of the research it supports.
- Help in the **formal publication of data sets**, as well as enabling the tracking of their usage to be tracked through citation and data licences.
- **Meet relevant legislation** and government guidance on the management and distribution of environmental information.

Difference between preservation and curation

Preservation

*The Phaistos Disk
1700 BC*

*Preserved, but information
content is zero!*

Digital curation entails (Wikipedia, 29/04/12)

- **Collecting (CEDA: ingestion)**
- **Providing search and retrieval (Services)**
- **Certification of the trustworthiness and integrity**
- **(documentation/metadata/provenance)**
- **Semantic and ontological continuity**
- **(an active process!)**

Who users CEDA? (Consumer Perspective)

Break down of 3713 users registered for specific CEDA data or services.

We don't have details for the **other 14,000** users!
April 2012.

User type:
72% University
Researchers.

Discipline:
38% Atmospheric and EO.
Full spectrum of other fields.

Science and Impact: CMIP5/AR5

CMIP5: Fifth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5)

Over **20 modelling groups** around the world sharing data from over **100 prescribed experiments** representing **thousands of years of simulations** with **millions of output datasets** (parameter/experiment/model) with up to **3 PB of requested output** and 10's of PB of likely output!

CMIP5 Archive Status

Last Update: *Friday, 27. April 2012 12:21AM (UTC)*

CMIP5 Federated Archive

Summary	
Modeling centers	24
Models	45
Experiments	110
Data nodes	19
Gateways	5
Datasets	43762
Size	1,104.64 TB
Files	2,602,812

Latest version only; no replicas.

Major intellectual challenge to organise the data. BADC in forefront of delivering the global federated data structure.
BADC key role as one of three “core” data centres; eventually to have a complete copy of requested output.

AR5: Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)

- ➔ **February 2011:** First model output available for analysis,
- ➔ **July 31, 2012:** By this date papers must be submitted for publication to be eligible for assessment by WG1,
- ➔ **March 15, 2013:** By this date papers **cited** by working group one (WG1) must be published or accepted.
- ➔ The IPCC's AR5 is scheduled to be published in September 2013.
- ➔ *Data in the CMIP5 archive which is used by WG1, WG2 or WG3, must be tagged in the BADC archive, for exposure by the (DECC funded) IPCC Data Distribution Centre.*

Science and Impact: FAAM

NERC/Met Office aircraft, deployed anywhere in the world!

Depend on access to BADC wherever and whenever they are (although we only provide UK 9-5 support, we have one staff member in the USA, which helps.)

Deployed on science missions measuring atmospheric properties, and occasionally in support of civil contingency (e.g. Eyjafjallajökull and recently over Elgin.)

Photo courtesy of Alan Gadian, NCAS

Figures from FAAM flight briefs B688 B689

EO data Sea Surface Temperature from space

Science and Impact: CEMS & ISIC

Facility for Climate and Environmental Monitoring from Space (CEMS);
"To provide robust evidence of how our planet is changing, and to enable better predictions"

From CEDA perspective: (1) A vehicle to support **engagement with the commercial community in exploiting EO and climate data** and; (2) A vehicle to provide resources for more **innovative approaches** to explore how we provide **services** (including computational virtualisation) for data users.

Complex relationship between CEMS and CEDA
(diagram courtesy of Reburn, Bennett, and Kershaw)

Visualisation: supported from CEDA (& e-Science)
(photo credit: Bennett)

UPSCALE

Picture courtesy of P-L Vidale & R. Schiemann, NCAS)

Ocean temperatures (in colour going from blue=cold to violet=warm) are shown in the background, while clouds (B/W scale) and precipitation (colour) are shown in the foreground. Over land, snow cover is shown in white.

HadGEM3-A (N512, GA3.0)

01 NOV 1986 01h UTC

UPSCALE

Model and animation by the JWCRP High-Resolution Climate Modelling Team

25 km resolution model run

<http://ncas-climate.nerc.ac.uk/HRCM>

The **largest ever** PRACE computational project, led by the UK, **dependent on BADC** to provide the data links and data analysis environment!

Science and Impact Implications: Volume, Heterogeneity, Diversity of Users

More Numbers!

Diagrams from IPCC AR5

The World in Global Climate Models

... and all the observations of this **diversity of processes** are needed to underpin and evaluate the simulations

... **probably** a vast underestimate in volume terms, and **definitely** a vast estimate in terms of the different versions needed for **differing communities!**
➔ **Data Analysis Problem!**

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CEDA Activities

CEDA Funding

Key points to note:

- Roughly half funding comes from NERC (NCAS and NCEO)
- Major input from project funding, including from the European Union and UK government (e.g. for European Network for Earth Simulation, and the IPCC Data Distribution Centre respectively).
- Significant funding for “informatics” e.g. “Data modelling” to support the European Commission's INSPIRE geospatial directive, and research funding from the international G8 “exascale” challenge for the ExArch project (Climate analytics on distributed exascale data archives – looking beyond what we're doing for CMIP5!)

CEDA in both STFC and NERC

